

Angelo Leogrande^{1}°*

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Public Debt as a Percentage of GDP at World Level

Between 2013 and 2021 it increased on average by 19.6% for the countries considered

The World Bank calculates the value of public debt as a percentage of GDP. Debt is the government's entire stock of fixed-term direct contractual obligations to others outstanding at a particular date. It includes domestic and foreign liabilities such as currency and cash deposits, securities other than stocks, and loans. It is the gross amount of government liabilities reduced by the amount of equity securities and financial derivatives held by the government. Because debt is a stock and not a flow, it is measured from a certain date, usually the last day of the fiscal year. The data analyzed refers to the period between 2013 and 2021. Only countries with a complete historical series in the period analyzed were considered.

Ranking of countries by value of public debt as a percentage of GDP in 2021. Croatia is in first place by value of public debt as a percentage of GDP in 2021 with a value of 687.99%, followed by Greece with 237.13%, from Japan with 217.61%, from the United Kingdom with 186.48%, and from Singapore with a value of 153.80%. In the middle of the table are Slovakia with a value of 79.25%, followed by Zambia with a value of 71.25%, Australia with a value of 70.18%, El Salvador with 65.55%, and from Ireland with 65.40%. Moldova closes the ranking with a value of 32.12%, followed by Estonia with 23.67%, Kazakhstan with 22.41%, Russia with 20.94% and Switzerland with a value of 20.30%. .

Ranking of countries by value of the percentage change in the value of public debt as a percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2021. Zambia is in first place by value of the growth rate of public debt as a percentage of GDP with a value of 194.11 % equal to 47.02 units, followed by Russia with a growth of 130.95% equal to 11.87%, by Kazakhstan with 106.74% equal to an amount of 11.57 units, by the Bahamas with 94.13% equal to 41.79 units, and from Peru with +93.87% equal to 41.79 units. In the middle of the table are the United Kingdom with a value of 31.74% equal to an amount of 44.92 units, followed by France with a value of 28.12% equal to an amount of 25.58 units, followed by Greece with a value of 27.66% equal to an amount of 51.38 units, Romania with a value of 26.82% equal to an amount of 11.77 units, and from the United States equal to a value of 26.00% equal to an amount of 24.84 units. Switzerland closes the ranking with a value equal to 0.43% equal to an amount of 0.09 units, followed by Hungary with a variation equal to an amount of -8.25% equal to an amount of -7.82 units, followed by Sweden with a value equal to -9.98% equal to an amount of -4.51%, followed by Iceland with -31.28% equal to an amount of -44.09 units and Ireland with a value of -50.37% equal to an amount of 66.38 units.

Machine Learning Algorithms for predicting the future value of public debt as a percentage of GDP. Below we compare eight different algorithms for predicting the future value of public debt as a percentage of GDP. The algorithms were trained with 70% of the data while the remaining 30% of

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

the data was used for the actual prediction. The algorithms were evaluated based on the ability to maximize the R-squared value and the ability to minimize a set of statistical errors, namely: Mean Absolute Error-MAE, Mean Squared Error-MSE, Root Mean Squared Error-RMSE. Specifically, we obtained the following ordering of the algorithms:

- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 5;
- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff value of 7;
- Gradient Boosted Trees Regression with a payoff value of 14;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 16;
- Simple Regression with a payoff value of 19;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 23;
- Polynomial Regression and PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 30.
- Therefore the Linear Regression algorithm appears to be the best performing algorithm in predictive terms. By applying the Linear Regression algorithm it is therefore possible to verify the following predictions:
- Australia with a variation from an amount of 70.18% up to a value of 68.98% or equal to a variation of -1.19 units equal to a value of -1.70%;
- Belgium with an increasing variation from an amount of 109.22% up to a value of 115.79% or a variation equal to an amount of 6.57 units equal to an amount of 6.01%;
- Estonia with a variation from an amount of 23.67% up to a value of 23.69% or equal to an amount of 0.03 units equal to a value of 0.11%;
- Georgia with a variation from an amount of 55.38% up to a value of 63.93% or a variation equal to an amount of 8.54 units equal to a value of 15.42%;
- Greece with a variation from an amount of 237.13% up to a value of 248.46% or a variation equal to an amount of 11.33 units equal to a value;
- Iceland with a variation from an amount of 96.87% up to a value of 99.15% or equal to an amount of 2.29 units equivalent to a value of 2.36%;
- Moldova with a decreasing variation from an amount of 32.12% up to a value of 28.17% or equal to an amount of -3.95% equal to -12.30%;
- Russia with a variation from an amount of 20.94% up to a value of 25.10% or a variation equal to an amount of 4.16 units equivalent to 19.85%;
- San Marino with a variation from an amount of 95.12% up to a value of 89.37% or a variation equal to -5.75 units equal to -6.04%;
- United States with an increasing variation from an amount of 120.37% up to a value of 121.58% or a variation equal to an amount of 1.21 units equal to a value of 1.01%;
- Zambia with a variation from an amount of 71.25% up to a value of 107.60% or a variation equal to 36.35 units equal to 51.02%;
- Brazil with an increasing variation from an amount of 86.09% up to a value of 102.99% or a variation equal to an amount of 16.90% equal to an amount of 19.63%.

On average, for the countries analyzed the value of public debt is predicted to grow from an amount of 84.86% up to a value of 91.23% or a variation equal to a value of 6.37 units equal to +7, 51%.

Conclusions. Public debt as a percentage of GDP increased on average by 19.6% for the countries considered. In particular, there was a peak in the growth of public debt as a percentage of GDP between 2019 and 2020 from an amount of 82.54% up to a value of 101.14% on average. Between 2020 and 2021 there was a reduction in public debt as a percentage of GDP from 101.14 to 95.58, always considering the average of the countries analyzed. The growth of public debt as a percentage of GDP affected all countries regardless of per capita income. Both low per capita income and high

per capita income countries have increased debt as a percentage of GDP. One of the reasons that has reduced the debt as a percentage of GDP is the contraction in GDP that occurred in connection with the Covid-19 pandemic. However, it is likely that the growth of public debt as a percentage of GDP will also continue in 2022 and 2023 following the mix of inflation and the economic crisis connected to the Russian-Ukrainian war. A period of high inflation, high interest rates and high public debts in connection with low economic growth could lead to a dimension of inefficiency in both the public and private sectors. In fact, the public sector is blocked by the high debt, which burdens especially countries without "*monetary sovereignty*". And high inflation together with the growth of interest rates and low economic growth prevent the private sector from performing effectively, creating conditions of low productivity in businesses and financial criticality in families.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. We are grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University "Giuseppe Degennaro" and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

References

Leogrande, A., Birardi, G., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2019). Italian Universities: Institutional Mandate and Communitarian Engagement. *European Journal of Educational Management*, 2(2), 85-110.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy. A Data-Driven Analysis. A Data-Driven Analysis (December 25, 2022).

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The smes innovation in europe. Available at SSRN 3964059.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. Available at SSRN 4032975.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT. In IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics (pp. 55-67).

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. Available at SSRN 4434206.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Determinants of CO2 Emissions in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4425121.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946

Appendix

Country Name	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Albania	70,58	73,32	79,86	80,74	75,89	64,57	75,70	83,89	82,38
Australia	37,58	41,74	46,51	54,69	53,28	54,49	60,25	69,40	70,18
Austria	87,70	95,80	95,08	94,69	89,41	84,22	83,09	99,87	94,32
Bahamas, The	44,40	46,17	48,29	50,76	53,46	57,24	57,64	83,97	86,19
Belgium	101,56	112,31	108,59	110,20	103,88	101,39	103,38	119,48	109,22
Brazil	57,23	58,46	67,54	73,42	83,67	86,61	92,57	98,71	86,09
Bulgaria	22,06	32,50	30,84	35,53	32,22	28,69	26,92	32,24	32,81
Canada	53,20	51,48	55,99	56,02	54,46	53,15	53,36	74,92	64,04
Colombia	67,10	47,98	53,28	66,91	66,73	71,65	72,70	91,12	79,78
Croatia	661,90	706,31	724,03	706,09	656,73	633,16	616,81	746,00	687,99
El Salvador	62,40	50,84	51,28	52,07	55,25	52,21	53,88	70,36	65,55
Estonia	13,80	13,95	13,12	14,07	13,43	13,46	14,05	23,76	23,67
France	90,97	97,55	97,98	102,26	102,22	101,62	104,96	123,28	116,55
Georgia	29,50	30,98	36,65	40,27	39,39	38,89	45,15	65,88	55,38
Greece	185,74	189,29	189,16	194,62	198,97	208,81	212,36	252,52	237,13
Hungary	94,73	98,67	96,40	96,78	91,99	86,55	83,37	96,00	86,91
Iceland	140,95	135,80	117,37	103,36	90,44	81,96	90,18	100,67	96,87
Indonesia	27,78	27,42	30,31	31,37	32,43	33,14	33,73	42,90	44,40
Ireland	131,78	121,21	88,56	85,33	76,65	75,18	69,54	71,74	65,40
Japan	186,56	192,11	194,58	193,23	193,49	197,33	198,02	216,06	217,61
Kazakhstan	10,84	12,65	19,31	16,77	16,93	21,99	18,48	23,72	22,41
Korea, Rep.	34,93	36,50	37,49	38,07	37,35	37,56	39,97	46,43	49,16
Lithuania	44,84	48,33	49,65	47,74	44,98	38,99	42,64	53,36	48,91
Malaysia	53,00	52,68	53,57	51,89	50,05	51,19	52,42	62,03	63,40
Moldova	19,92	21,07	23,31	32,25	29,67	27,51	25,45	33,96	32,12
New Zealand	46,45	43,92	42,94	41,42	38,66	36,62	32,75	46,15	50,99

Peru	18,39	19,57	22,87	23,71	24,75	25,73	26,53	34,67	35,66
Romania	43,88	46,27	45,17	47,28	44,33	42,56	43,21	57,11	55,65
Russian Federation	9,07	11,20	13,54	14,24	16,33	16,17	17,28	22,99	20,94
San Marino	54,02	53,32	56,93	57,33	54,59	55,94	55,09	98,35	95,12
Singapore	99,45	99,61	103,32	109,06	109,32	110,76	127,85	152,04	153,80
Slovak Republic	63,21	65,88	64,83	66,42	64,35	63,78	63,15	78,41	79,25
Spain	92,31	105,57	105,40	106,78	107,29	107,97	112,05	140,40	135,82
Sweden	45,17	49,45	47,43	46,19	43,95	42,26	38,67	43,99	40,66
Switzerland	20,22	20,61	20,44	19,38	20,28	18,68	18,95	20,91	20,30
Turkiye	32,12	31,35	29,06	30,07	29,86	29,41	34,13	41,97	42,73
United Kingdom	141,56	150,58	147,61	156,00	161,09	157,80	160,02	195,39	186,48
United States	95,53	95,77	96,43	98,50	97,69	99,06	100,81	126,23	120,37
Zambia	24,22	44,40	49,41	46,43	52,28	59,71	61,93	103,70	71,25
Media	79,91	82,89	83,44	84,41	82,25	81,23	82,54	101,14	95,58

Statistical Errors	ANN	PNN	Simple Regression	Gradient Boosted Trees regression
R ²	0,650	-124,722	0,776	0,851
mean absolute error	0,051	0,318	0,026	0,017
mean squared error	0,024	0,289	0,002	0,001
root mean squared error	0,154	0,538	0,041	0,028
Statistical Errors	Random Forest Regression	Tree Ensemble Regression	Linear Regression	Polynomial Regression
R ²	0,4010	0,9645	0,9850	-5,2738
mean absolute error	0,0170	0,0109	0,0073	0,2884
mean squared error	0,0010	0,0000	0,0000	0,4158

root mean squared error	0,0249	0,0163	0,0104	0,6448
-------------------------	--------	--------	--------	--------

Ranking of Machine Learning Algorithms by Statistical Performance in Prediction					
Algorithms	R²	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error	Sum
Linear Regression	1	1	2	1	5
Tree Ensemble Regression	2	2	1	2	7
Gradient Boosted Trees regression	3	4	3	4	14
Simple Regression	4	5	5	5	19
ANN	5	6	6	6	23
Random Forest Regression	6	3	4	3	16
Polynomial Regression	7	7	8	8	30
PNN	8	8	7	7	30

Rank	2021	Prediction	Var Ass	Var Per
Australia	70,18	68,98	-1,19	-1,70
Belgium	109,22	115,79	6,57	6,01
Brazil	86,09	102,99	16,90	19,63
Estonia	23,67	23,69	0,03	0,11
Georgia	55,38	63,93	8,54	15,42
Greece	237,13	248,46	11,33	4,78
Iceland	96,87	99,15	2,29	2,36
Moldova	32,12	28,17	-3,95	-12,30
Russian Federation	20,94	25,10	4,16	19,85
San Marino	95,12	89,37	-5,75	-6,04
United States	120,37	121,58	1,21	1,01
Zambia	71,25	107,60	36,35	51,02
Mean	84,86	91,23	6,37	7,51